

Map 38 • THESSUP 4
INTELLIGIBILITY VALUES

Map 34. THESSCITY 4
CONTROL VALUES of TQs
40% highest C.V. — TQs

Map 35. THESSALY 4
 CHOICE VALUES
 10% highest CH.V.

Map 36 • THESSALY 4
MOVEMENT INTERFACE

Map 37. THESSUP 4
CHOICE VALUES
10% highest CH.V.

Map 38 THESSUP 4
MOVEMENT INTERFACE

Map 39. THESSALY 4
CHOICE VALUES OF CITY-
QUARTERS
10% highest CH.V.

Map 40. THESSALONICA 5
AXIAL MAP

Map 41. THESSALY 5

INTEGRATION MAP

5% most integrated

lines (Int. core)

50% most segregated

lines

Map 48, THESSALY 5
CONTROL VALUES
10% highest C.V.

Map 44. THESSCITY 5
INTELLIGIBILITY VALUES

Map 45. THESSUP 5
CONTROL VALUES
10% highest C.V.

Map 46 • THESSUP 5
INTELLIGIBILITY VALUES

Map 47. THESSCITY 5
 CHOICE VALUES
 10% highest CH.V.

Map 48 • THESSALY 5
MOVEMENT INTERFACE

Map 49. THESSUP 5
CHOICE VALUES
10% highest CH.V.

Map 50 . THESSUP 5
MOVEMENT INTERFACE

Ph. 1. "Ladadika" and part of C.B.D.

Ph.2. Vlais - Vatikiotis - Pazarakia markets and C.B.D. in the background.

Ph.3. Vlalis-Vatikiotis-Pazarakia markets

Ph.4. Vlais - Vatikiotis - Pazarakia markets and the city's C.B.D.

Ph.5. Vialis-Vatikiotis-Pazarakia >II< St. Minas area and C.B.D.

Ph.6. "Ladadika" and part of C.B.D.

Ph.7. St. Minas area > II < Ph.8. "Ano-Polis"

Ph.θ. "Ano-Polis"

Ph. 9. "Ano Polis".